

SOCIAL PARTNERSHIP EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT MECHANISM AND TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE

EDILITA S. VARGAS¹

EDILBERTO Z. ANDAL²

13-s-med-062@lspu.edu.ph

0000-0002-9095-4734

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The study sought to determine the perception on the Social Partnership, Effective Management Mechanism and Teachers' Performance. It sought to answer the succeeding questions about Social Partnership, Effective Management Mechanism and the perception on Teachers' Performance. Furthermore, the study identified the relationship between the Social Partnership, Effective Management Mechanism and Teachers' Performance. The study conducted using descriptive survey method through google form. Administered to the seven school of cluster IV, Calamba City during the school year 2020 -2021. Data were collected and analyzed. The result of the study shows that Teachers-respondent Perceived the social partnership as "Highly Practiced". This shows that respondents prefer work in collaboration with the other staff and parents in generating projects for the school development. also, the study reveals the Effective Management Mechanisms as "Highly Effective". Based on the study about the teachers' performance deals with the level of performance of teachers as "Outstanding" interpretation. It implies the used a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills. The Findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the following conclusion: The Study being tested states that there is significant relationship between social partnership and Teachers' Performance and there is existence of significant relationship between effective management mechanism and teachers' performance. Therefore, the null hypotheses were not sustained. Based on findings and conclusions the following recommendations are suggested for educational practice: In order to enhance or further improve the teachers' performance there should be strong partnership and open communication must be present to easily identify address the needs of the schools and learners. To have an effective management mechanism they must also considered social partnership that provide and have the same goal to help and support the needs of the schools and learners.

Keywords: Education, Qualitative Research, survey, Philippines